

The London School of Economics and Political Science
Department of Psychological and Behavioural Science

**You Are What You Read:
A Conjoint Analysis of News Consumption in the United States
Following the Roe v. Wade Overruling**

Supervised By

Dr. Georgios Melios

Submitted By

Candidate no. 28863

MSc Behavioural Science

London, 16 August 2022

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Abstract

News consumption behaviour on social media has become a growing source of intrigue as debates around polarisation and misinformation escalate in the United States and around the world. Yet few studies have investigated the determinants of news consumption and the importance of partisan bias. A conjoint experiment was conducted among the United States population to explore the attributes that are influential in guiding news consumption decision-making. Abortion related news was used, just weeks after the US Supreme Court overturning of *Roe v. Wade*. In line with information seeking and avoidance theory, the findings indicate a general aversion to out-party news, with this effect being larger for Democrats than Republicans. Results also indicate preferences for news articles shared by those who share similar characteristics including partisan affiliation, religiosity, and gender. The findings are consistent with the theory of in-group bias. The results provide a roadmap for policy interventions aimed at reducing polarisation generally and at encouraging more diverse reading behaviour, and these are discussed throughout the paper.

1. Introduction

More than 70% of Americans consumed news on social media in 2020, compared to just over 10% in 2008 (Pew Research Center, 2021; Pew Research Center, 2008). In that time, the United States public has become significantly more polarised. *Political polarisation* is defined as the clustering of attitudes around two or more contrasting positions, and the dispersing of these positions, and the people who hold them, from one another (DiMaggio, Evans, & Bryson, 1996). The Pew Research Center (2017) has found significant increases in political polarisation in the United States in the last two decades, and while there are many reasons for the increase, the literature suggests that increasingly homogenous news consumption on social media has been a significant contributor (Van Bavel, Rathje, Harris, Robertson, & Sternisko, 2021).

Social media platforms use personalisation algorithms to feed people content they find interesting (Pariser, 2011). While this is a useful tactic for engaging people on the platform, it aggregates users into homophilic clusters, called filter bubbles, in which they are exposed only to news that confirms their own beliefs, leading to those beliefs becoming more and more polarised (Cinelli, Morales, Galeazzi, Quattrociochi, & Starnini, 2021; Levy, 2021). *Filter bubbles* (also called *echo chambers*) are defined as situations in which individuals are only exposed to opinions with which they agree (Garimella, De Francisci Morales, Gionis, & Mathioudakis, 2018).

Encouraging people to read more diverse material is thus an important goal. Indeed, researchers have found that diverse media diets involving exposure to counter-attitudinal news promotes depolarisation (Levy, 2021; Parsons, 2010). In order to illuminate which policies may encourage diverse reading consumption, however, it is important to understand the determinants of news consumption, which is the aim of the current study.

The paper contributes to the existing knowledge base surrounding news consumption in three ways. Firstly, it uses the innovative method of a conjoint analysis to provide a deep insight into how people make decisions surrounding which news articles they read. Conjoint analysis was developed as a market research technique, but has more recently been used in the domain of political science to examine the effects of many features of complex choices on individual preferences (Leeper, Hobolt, & Tilley, 2020). Recent papers using a conjoint approach have focused on immigration (Donnalaja, 2022; Hainmueller & Hopkins, 2015), voting (Breitenstein, 2019; Franchino & Zucchini, 2015), and vaccine preferences (Kreps, Dasgupta, Brownstein, Hswen, & Kriner, 2021; Motta, 2021).

Secondly, it uses a measure of partisan bias in news articles, the use of which is novel in academic research, to score articles on a partisan spectrum. The measure is developed by Read Across The Aisle (2022), a company with a mission to encourage more diverse media consumption behaviour, and they use methods such as crowdsourcing to rate news outlets in terms of political bias. While this measure has not been used in academic research thus far, crowdsourcing has proved an accurate tool in the political science literature (Pennycook & Rand, 2019).

Finally, it assesses news consumption behaviour around abortion in the aftermath of the United States Supreme Court's overturning of *Roe v Wade*. Abortion is an issue that is extremely polarising, with partisanship being one of the most significant determinants of voting behaviour on abortion (Schechter, 2001). It is, therefore, a suitable topic for this study aimed at investigating the determinants of news consumption as the opposing stances are highly variable between political parties yet consistent within them.

The experimental design roughly follows Mukerjee & Yang (2021) who examined news preferences using a conjoint analysis. After completing a questionnaire about demographics and partisanship, respondents complete a number of tasks in which they pick which article they would prefer to read from a choice of two. In line with the theory on selective exposure and confirmation bias, it is expected that individuals will avoid out-party news and seek in-party news. The hypothesis is tested using several stages of regression analysis and by computing the average marginal component effect (AMCE) for each attribute.

The paper is structured as follows. [Section 2](#) gives a background of polarisation and news consumption in the United States, touching on previous and potential policy approaches, before discussing the issue of abortion in the United States. [Section 3](#) briefly explores the use and applicability of conjoint experiments in political science. In [Section 4](#), the hypotheses are outlined with reference to supporting literature. [Section 5](#) outlines the experimental design. [Section 6](#) describes the analytical framework, results are reported and discussed in [Section 7](#) and [Section 8](#) respectively, and a conclusion of the study follows.

2. Background

News consumption behaviour is interesting primarily insofar as it contributes to political polarisation. Polarisation happens as behavioural biases interact with the external environment to govern how people consume media, leading to politically biased media diets. Social media platforms are designed in such a way as to amplify the effect of existing biases, nudging people towards attitude-confirming content. This section of the paper first gives a background on political polarisation in the United States, including its causes and consequences, before exploring the behavioural issues surrounding news consumption. Policy measures to address these issues are briefly outlined, followed by a discussion of abortion in the United States.

2.1 Political Polarisation in the United States

As previously stated, polarisation refers to the dispersing of attitudes and individuals around conflicting views, and recent decades have seen an increase in such dispersion among the United States public. *Figure 1* shows the distribution of Americans on a 10-item scale of political values between 1994 and 2017 (Pew Research Center, 2017).

Figure 1
Distribution of Republicans and Democrats on a 10-Item Scale of Political Values

Notes: See [Appendix A](#) for 10-item scale.

Naturally, dispersion has not only occurred among the public, but is also reflected within the US Congress. Between the 90th Congress (1967-69) and the 115th Congress (2017-19), the views of Republicans and Democrats have shifted such that there is virtually no overlap in their ideologies. Findings based on roll-call votes show that whereas in the late 60s the ideological positions of Democrat and Republican senators and representatives overlapped, today they are completely separate such that the most conservative Democrat holds a position that is more liberal than the most liberal Republican (Fiorina, 2017). Ideological divergence not only leads to parties that are more distant from one another, but can also lead to a tendency for partisans to develop dislike and distrust for each other, a phenomenon called affective polarisation (Druckman & Levendusky, 2019). Rogowski & Sutherland (2016) found that US citizens often form affective evaluations of politicians based on their ideological positions

Distance between partisans can be further increased through the process of social sorting. Social sorting occurs when political parties become increasingly linked with particular social identities such as race or religion, which reduces cross-pressures on political behaviour (Mason & Wronski, 2018). Such a phenomenon has been observed in the US (Mason, 2016) and can result in parties becoming more homogenous and emotionally reactive. This is because when the identities of party members are increasingly uniform, the perceived difference between parties appears greater.

There is much research devoted to investigating the consequences of polarisation, and it has been found to be harmful to democracy in a number of ways. Polarisation can lead to alienated voters (Layman, Carsey, & Horowitz, 2006), reduced civility in political debate (Jamieson & Falk, 2000), and legislative gridlocks in Congress (Binder, 2004; Jones, 2001). While these hinder the political process, polarisation has also been found to influence familial and social relationships. Chen & Rohla (2018) found that in the wake of the 2016 election, Americans were averse to cross-partisan dialogue within their families. Another study from Iyengar, Sood, & Lelkes (2012) demonstrated that the percentage of Americans who would be unhappy if their child married a person of the opposite party has increased by approximately 35 percentage points in the last 50 years. Indeed, Iyengar, Konitzer, & Tedin (2018) have recently demonstrated that 80.5% of married couples share a party identification. Chopik & Motyl (2016) have also found that it is more difficult to make friends if one is living in a politically incongruent area.

Social media has been found to exasperate the problem by increasing the distance between partisans in their virtual lives as the aggregation of users into like-minded clusters on social networks decreases the probability of encountering individuals with opposing viewpoints (Gimpel & Hui, 2015). Within these groups, polarisation proceeds through what is dubbed 'The Law of Group Polarisation' (Sunstein, 1999). In this process, given a group of individuals in general agreement on a certain topic, say, that abortion is immoral, deliberation among the group moves each member, and the group as a whole, to a more extreme position – in this scenario, to a greater opposition to abortion.

As well as reducing exposure to opposing individuals, social media algorithms reduce exposure to opposing content, which has been demonstrated to worsen polarisation (Cinelli, Morales, Galeazzi, Quattrociocchi, & Starnini, 2021). Users are often unaware of the way in which these algorithms work, and may therefore be unaware of the partisan bias in their media diet (Rader & Gray, 2015). Dubois & Blank (2018) find that those with more diverse news consumption tend to avoid echo chambers and their polarising effects. This makes it important to understand what drives individual news consumption behaviour so more diverse media diets can be encouraged.

2.2 News Consumption in the United States

As the aforementioned statistics demonstrate, news consumption in the United States has largely, though not exclusively, become a story of news consumption on social media. This section of the paper outlines the behavioural biases governing how people consume media, touching on their interaction with the design of social networks, before exploring policy measures.

2.2.1 Behavioural Issues Surrounding News Consumption

The three main behavioural issues surrounding news consumption are confirmation bias, selective exposure, and in-group bias. Each of these interact with each other and with the external environment to influence the way in which individuals consume media, often leading to politically biased media diets. They will be discussed in turn.

Confirmation Bias

Confirmation bias is defined as seeking out and attaching more validity or weight to information that is congruent with one's own beliefs (Williams, Kern, & Waters, 2016). Confirmation bias often leads to biased news consumption as individuals disregard information that is counter-attitudinal. The concept of belief based utility gives a good explanation of this phenomenon.

Belief based utility is the idea that people gain utility from their beliefs, and as a result are incentivised to protect them as they would their possessions (Loewenstein & Molnar, 2018). As a result, individual beliefs become rigid, even in the face of countering evidence. Loewenstein, Weber, Hsee, & Welch (2001) formulated the 'risk as feelings' hypothesis, which gives a great explanation for belief based utility. The risk as feelings hypothesis states that emotion plays a significant role at the moment of decision making, and emotional reactions often diverge from cognitive assessments of risk to produce irrational decisions. An example of this in the political landscape was demonstrated by Kaplan, Gimbel, & Harris (2016). In their experiment they showed that when presented with political statements that are conflicting with one's own beliefs, those least likely to change their minds show greater signal in the amygdala. The amygdala is the part of the brain associated with anxiety and the fight or flight response (Skuse, Morris, & Lawrence, 2003). Thus individuals with the most rigid beliefs often experience a negative emotional reaction of risk when encountering statements that challenge their opinions. These individuals are, therefore, incentivised to avoid such information as a result of the negative psychological and physiological reactions associated with such an encounter.

Selective Exposure

Selective exposure is tightly linked to confirmation bias, but differs such that while the latter largely refers to judging the veracity of information, selective exposure is more concerned with the process by which people filter out information that challenges their beliefs and focus on that which confirms their beliefs (Stroud, 2010). When selecting content, this could entail avoiding outlets or headlines that indicate contrary views to one's opinion and sticking with outlets that are known and trusted. Such a practice leads to a biased media diet, and has a reinforcing relationship with polarisation, such that selecting content that confirms one's beliefs pushes people further down an ideological hole, which in turn determines the content to which one exposes themselves. As previously stated, social networks encourage filtering through their use of personalised news feeds, creating clusters that are more distinct and less connected than would emerge without technological filters (Geschke, Lorenz, & Holtz, 2019).

Another way in which information is filtered down to people is through informational and reputational cascades. According to Herbert Simon (1997) and the concept of bounded rationality, people can only take in a certain amount of information at one time, and as a result often defer to the views of others to form their opinions. Informational and reputational cascades differ such that in the former, people believe a proposition simply because there are many other people who have shared it, while in the latter, individuals may not believe in a particular view, but share it anyway so as to preserve their reputation within their social network (Sunstein, 2018). Participation in such cascades could be indicated by reading information that is endorsed or shared by individuals for whom one has a certain amount of respect or reverence, or by those with whom one agrees politically. Cascades can be particularly dangerous when the content which is spread is misinformation, as can often happen. Pennycook & Rand (2021) have found that among those who share fake news, most are unaware of its falsity.

In-group Bias and Social Identity Theory

In-group bias (or *in-group favouritism*) refers to differences in the mental processing of in-group and out-group members or cues related to each identity, such as a national flag (Saarinen et al., 2021). The aggregation of individuals into groups, be it political parties or clusters on social media, allows in-group bias to develop as it promotes intergroup hostility and distrust through the behavioural and psychological mechanisms described by *social identity theory* (Rubin & Hewstone, 2004). According to social identity theory, in-group bias develops due to social competition, realistic competition, and consensual discrimination. Social competition occurs when individual identity becomes synonymous with group identity and individuals compete with other groups to elevate their own group's status (Tajfel, 1978). Realistic competition occurs as groups compete for limited physical resources (Turner, 1975). Consensual discrimination occurs when groups behave in a way to prevail the status hierarchy with which each group agrees, showing in-group and out-group favouritism respectively (Tajfel, Turner, Austin, & Worchel, 1979).

In-group bias influences news consumption as it interacts with confirmation bias and selective exposure to encourage individuals to avoid and discount information that are perceived as coming from the other group, which could take the form of avoiding certain newspapers or articles shared by opposing party members. As groups become more disconnected and dialogue between them is discouraged, they can create misperceptions of one another, which has been shown to be a significant contributor to polarisation (Ahler & Sood, 2018; Bavel et al., 2020; Lees & Cikara, 2020).

2.2.2 Policy Interventions

Policy interventions to encourage diverse news consumption have a long history. In the 1970s, the US Supreme Court ruled that the government has the authority to require television and radio broadcasters to give an opportunity for diverse views to be aired on their platforms (Sunstein, 2018). Such a ruling is aimed at increasing exposure to diverse media, but the question remains as to whether this strategy is effective. Understanding the determinants of news consumption could prove valuable when designing such interventions. For example, if individuals place a greater importance on which outlets news comes from than on who endorsed them, perhaps a must-carry law requiring outlets to give both sides of a debate would be optimal. If, on the other hand, endorsements are more influential, interventions aimed at encouraging prominent figures to lead by example and work together on tough issues could prove to be more effectual. Potential and trialled measures can largely be viewed under the three levers of education, policy, and design, as suggested by Renee Diresta of the Stanford Internet Observatory (Nudgestock, 2021).

An educational intervention that is being trialled in the United States is the implementation of news literacy programs. Such programs educate people on the importance of reading diverse material as well as on how to determine the credibility of news. They have been trialled in universities (Fleming, 2014) and among the public by organisations such as The News Literacy Project (2022).

Considering public policy interventions, disclosure policies have proved effective in other areas. Requiring disclosure of business practices was effective in reducing environmentally destructive policies of companies in the United States (Hamilton, 2005). By allowing the public access to such knowledge, businesses become more accountable for their actions. Such a strategy could be useful in encouraging diverse media consumption. By giving the public clear knowledge of the algorithmic function of social media companies and how they lead to narrow media diets and polarisation, the public may take steps to avoid such manipulation and the businesses themselves may be more incentivised to implement other policies that are less harmful.

Regarding design, one business policy advocated for by Frances Haugen, a former Facebook employee who alerted the public about Facebook's harmful practices, is altering the way in which social media algorithms function (Hao, 2021). This would involve suggesting to people a more diverse range of news articles rather than the current system which feeds people information with which they agree. Such an intervention could prove attractive to social media companies in the future as socially responsible practices become more important to customers. Apple have made privacy a selling point in recent years (Lukoff et al., 2021), and other companies could potentially make a Diversity of Viewpoints (DOVE) policy a socially conscious goal and a selling point for their company. Facebook lost users for the first time in their history in 2021 (Hart, 2022) and such a change may be what the public wants.

Another design intervention being trialled by a company called Read Across The Aisle (2022) is informing people of the partisan bias in their media diet. They use an indicator, shown in *Figure 2*, which moves depending on which news outlets users read, to alert individuals to their partisan bias.

Figure 2
Read Across The Aisle

The political leaning of outlets is determined using ratings from publications, polling data, and crowdsourcing (Brightwell, 2017). Crowdsourcing has been used as an accurate tool in this sphere by Pennycook & Rand (2019) who crowdsourced judgements of news headline veracity. Crowdsourcing is also beneficial for scalability, as it makes the project much more scalable than if social media platforms had to rate the leaning of every outlet themselves. The use of this measure in the current study will illuminate how large a role partisan bias plays in decision-making surrounding news consumption.

2.3 Abortion in the United States

Abortion has long been a divisive issue in the United States (Devins, 2016). In 1973, the Supreme Court ruled that state prohibitions on abortions were unconstitutional, legalising abortion in the landmark case, *Roe v. Wade* (Heymann & Barzelay, 1973). Since then, *Roe v. Wade* has been one of the most high profile decisions ever rendered by the Supreme Court. When asked to name a case that has been decided by the Supreme Court, most Americans who can name one choose *Roe v. Wade*, which is eight times more likely to be named than *Brown v. Board of Education* (Greenhouse & Siegel, 2011). The case has become synonymous with political conflict and partisanship. Partisanship has been shown to be one of the most significant determinants of voting behaviour on abortion, with Republicans and Democrats adopting pro-life and pro-choice stances respectively (Schechter, 2001).

Recent events have again thrown the issue of abortion into the spotlight. On 24th June 2022, the Supreme Court overturned *Roe v. Wade*, allowing states to decide whether abortion will be legal in their state (Lewandowska, 2022). Thirteen states enacted trigger laws which would criminalise abortion at the moment the ruling was overturned, with a further thirteen states likely to follow suit (Nash & Guarnieri, 2022). The ruling sent shockwaves across the public, prompting widespread backlash and protests, and calls for changes to be made to the Supreme Court (Tanne, 2022). The current study uses abortion-related news to assess the determinants of news consumption in the aftermath of the judicial ruling. Such work will provide insight around feelings on abortion, as well as on partisan news consumption in general, as the identification of each party with the opposing stances on abortion makes it a suitable topic for extrapolation to other divisive political issues.

3. Conjoint Analysis in Political Science

Conjoint experiments are a useful tool when trying to answer questions of preferences. Historically they have been very popular in marketing as a market research technique (Raghavarao, Wiley, & Chitturi, 2010), but in recent years, conjoint designs have been used in political science. Conjoint experiments have been used to reveal preferences about immigration (Donnalaja, 2022; Hainmueller & Hopkins, 2015), voting in elections and referenda (Breitenstein, 2019; Loewen, Rubenson, & Spirling, 2012), perceptions of opinion poll credibility (Dawson, 2022), and acceptance of vaccines (Kreps, Dasgupta, Brownstein, Hswen, & Kriner, 2021; Motta, 2021; Sun et al., 2020). [Appendix B](#) gives a breakdown of conjoint experiments conducted in the political science literature according to a literature review conducted by Bansak, Hainmueller, Hopkins, & Yamamoto (2019).

Conjoint designs are useful for answering political questions such as: What characteristics do people care about when deciding who gets to immigrate to their country? Does religion or education play a bigger role in choosing which candidate to vote for? What characteristics of vaccines make them appealing for the public? They can also be used to explore very interesting questions around in-group bias. In the paper by Rubin & Hewstone (2004) discussed above, they explore in-group and out-group favouritism using an interesting example of a black policeman in the United States. According to social identity theory, a black police officer may begin to discriminate against their racial in-group when a police force contains norms that prescribe such discrimination. A conjoint analysis could potentially reveal which characteristics play a more influential role in such situations of discrimination. In a similar fashion, conjoint experiments can answer the question of what would make a Republican vote for a Democratic candidate, or when does a certain policy or characteristic overcome loyalty to the in-group, or whether the endorser of a news source can encourage people to read content which is counter-attitudinal.

Conjoint designs are, therefore, very useful in political science studies aimed at revealing preferences, such as the current study. Though their use in the political science literature is relatively recent, they provide an innovative method to answer some of the most interesting and impactful political questions of our times.

4. Hypotheses

A conjoint experiment allows us to evaluate the importance of various attributes in determining which news articles individuals choose to read. In this section of the paper, each attribute is considered in turn and the literature surrounding each is discussed to indicate its expected effect on news consumption.

4.1 Partisan Bias

The current experiment tests the effect of partisan bias on news consumption. Bias is determined using the measure developed by Read Across The Aisle (2022) and the discussion above of confirmation bias and selective exposure provide an indication of its expected effect.

The theories of information seeking and avoidance suggest that individuals seek information with which they agree and avoid information with which they do not agree or which they find displeasing (Yang & Kahlor, 2013). Researchers have found evidence for politically motivated selective exposure of news in which individuals prefer attitudinal-consistent news rather than counter-attitudinal news (Iyengar & Hahn, 2009; Stroud, 2011; Westerwick, Johnson, & Knobloch-Westerwick, 2017; Winter, Metzger, & Flanagin, 2016). Studies have also found evidence for these behaviours regarding COVID-19 and personal health information (Case, Andrews, Johnson, & Allard, 2005; Kim, Ahn, Atkinson, & Kahlor, 2020) and one would expect to see similar behaviours surrounding information on abortion. Evidence on the importance of seeking and avoidance respectively is mixed with Garrett (2009) finding that seeking plays a bigger role than avoidance and Mukerjee & Yang (2021) finding the opposite.

In terms of the current study, the evidence suggests that one would expect to see a positive effect of in-party bias on news consumption and a negative effect of out-party bias on news consumption. The use of the partisan bias measurement in this study allows us to test the effect of various different levels and strengths of bias outlined in [Section 6.1](#).

4.2 Endorser Partisanship

The conjoint design also tests for the effect of endorser partisanship. News sharing on social media has become an interesting area for research in recent decades (Kümpel, Karnowski, & Keyling, 2015) and including endorser partisanship mimics the real world in which many people encounter news which is shared by others on social platforms.

The discussion of informational and reputational cascades, and in-group bias, above demonstrates the potential importance of endorser partisanship on news consumption. Messing & Westwood (2014) have found that endorsement can be even more influential than partisan source affiliation on selective exposure. Endorser partisanship follows much of the same logic as partisan bias, and given the discussion of cascades and in-group bias, it is expected that individuals will be more likely to select news that is shared by people in the same political party as them. It will be interesting to see effect sizes for endorser partisanship relative to the partisan bias measure.

4.3 Endorser Gender

Endorser gender is also included to mimic a real world news navigation scenario, though it is especially interesting given the asymmetrical impact on women regarding decisions around abortion law. Abortion is largely positioned as a women's rights issue (Kaczor, 2014) and, as a result, news shared by women may be more likely to be selected than that shared by men. Though feasible, it is expected that endorser gender will not play a significant role in determining news consumption in the current study.

4.4 Endorser Religiosity

Roe v. Wade has long been positioned as a religious issue (Potts, 1998). Generally, individual religiosity has been found to be a significant predictor of attitudes towards abortion, with studies finding that those who are religious tend to be stronger in opposition to abortion (Hess & Rueb, 2005; Ogland & Verona, 2011; Wilcox, 1992) and that the countries with the most restrictive abortion policies are those where high levels of religiosity persist (Minkenberg, 2002). Religiosity has also been found to influence selective exposure to information (Bobkowski, 2009; McFarland & Warren Jr, 1992).

Overall, endorser religion is expected to have a negligible effect on news consumption. However, one may expect that this result masks heterogeneity across respondents. Given the conflation of abortion policy with religion, one might expect that respondents who are religious themselves will be more likely to select news articles from endorsers that are religious relative to endorsers that are not religious. For the purposes of this experiment, respondents are asked to select the faith to which they belong to account for any differences that may appear based on each religion.

5. Experimental Design

The experimental design and data analyses methods are preregistered with the AsPredicted framework (Walsh, 2022). Ethical approval to conduct the experiment was received from LSE on 28th July 2022 and data collection began on 29th July 2022.

5.1 Overview

A conjoint experiment was conducted using respondents from the United States population on the survey platform Prolific. A conjoint analysis is conducted to measure the importance of various attributes, each with different levels, to understand which factors drive individual decision-making. Participant anonymity was maintained at all times and the number of tasks was determined to optimise D-efficiency and internal validity.

5.2 Participants

Participants were recruited through the online survey platform Prolific. Prolific is preferred over other online tools for its high level of transparency and usability which leads to good quality responses (Palan & Schitter, 2018). Respondents were recruited from the United States population and were required to be English-speaking and over 18 years old at the time of the study.

The appropriate sample size for conjoint experiments is a question for which no clear answer is offered, with different figures offered among the literature (McCullough, 2002). Sawtooth Software offers a useful guideline adopted from simulation work done on a logistic regression by Peduzzi, Concato, Kemper, Holford, & Feinstein (1996). The Sawtooth guideline (Bock, 2019) says that the minimum sample size should be:

$$n \geq \frac{1000c}{qa}$$

Where:

q is the number of tasks in the exercise,

a is the number of alternatives per question (excluding the “none of these”), and

c is the maximum number of levels of any attribute.

For example, in our study with maximum attribute levels of 7, 13 tasks, and 2 alternatives, then:

$$n \geq \frac{1000 \times 7}{13 \times 2} = 270$$

Here, the 1000 represents the minimum number of times each attribute level will appear in the study. Other sources have suggested 500 is adequate (Orme, 2006), but that was intended as a minimum threshold, and 1000 or more representations per main-effect level is preferred. The Sawtooth guideline recommends a minimum sample size of 270 for this experiment. This study thus recruits over 350 respondents as a result of the recommendation along with budget considerations.

5.3 Materials

See [Appendix C](#) for the complete set of materials used in the experiment.

5.3.1 Pilot Survey

A pilot study was conducted to ensure the survey materials were fit for purpose. Many thanks are offered to those who provided valuable feedback to be incorporated into the experiment before beginning data collection.

5.3.2 Informed Consent

In compliance with the LSE Research Ethics Policy and Procedures (n.d.) and LSE's guidelines on informed consent (LSE, 2021), informed consent was gathered from all participants at the beginning of the experiment. The informed consent form outlined information about the study, participants right to withdrawal, and the contact details of the experimenter in case of questions or concerns.

5.3.3 Socio-Demographic Background

Participants first completed questions on their socio-demographic background, including education, religion etc. This was done to enable the observation of any heterogeneity across these characteristics. Though common practice in many experiments, it is of special interest for the current study. Polarisation has been found to have a relationship with demographic characteristics such as income (Grechyna, 2016), as has access to information (Swenson & Ghertner, 2020), and in the current study which expects that in-group bias may have an effect, demographic factors are of interest as these are often the lines on which groups are separated (Molenberghs, 2013).

5.3.4 Partisanship

Respondents are then asked questions about their partisanship, first about their party affiliation, and then about the strength of this affiliation. Participants are also asked about their feelings toward both Republicans and Democrats using a feeling thermometer rating in line with the approach by the American National Election Studies (2019). This is done so the determinants of news consumption can be measured in terms of attributes with in-party and out-party leanings. The analyses can be performed conditional on partisanship to investigate heterogeneity across groups.

5.3.5 Conjoint Analysis Task

The survey then moves on to the conjoint analysis task, in which respondents are presented with articles with varying attributes and asked questions about their preferences. Article attributes included in this design are *political bias*, *endorser partisanship*, *endorser gender*, and *endorser religiosity*. Choices are presented in pairs and participants must pick which article they would rather read. The evidence suggests that pairwise designs are better at mimicking real-world behaviour than other conjoint or vignette designs (Hainmueller, Hangartner, & Yamamoto, 2015). The use of forced choice questions is common in conjoint experiments in the literature (Bansak, Hainmueller, Hopkins, & Yamamoto, 2019).

The number of tasks to give respondents is another question which provides many possible answers. An advantage of conjoint experiments is that researchers can obtain many observations from survey respondents without compromising validity, making conjoint designs a highly cost effective strategy. Researchers must be careful, however, not to present too many tasks as this could result in satisficing, a situation in which respondents take shortcuts to complete the survey faster (Krosnick, 1999). Bansak, Hainmueller, Hopkins, & Yamamoto (2018) demonstrated that one could use as many as 30 choice tasks before receiving a degradation in responses. For the purposes of this experiment, participants will complete 13 tasks. This is well within recommendations and also gives a study completion time within the guidelines provided by Qualtrics (2022) to ensure survey completion and maintain internal validity. 13 tasks also gave an optimal D-efficiency, which ensures efficient estimates of potential effects, as attributes are uncorrelated and balanced in their levels (Valet, Sauer, & Tolsma, 2021).

6. Analytical Framework

6.1 Attributes and Levels

As mentioned, conjoint experiments allow researchers to measure the effect of various attributes on respondent preferences (Lohrke, Holloway, & Woolley, 2010), in this case, regarding news consumption. To maximise the external validity of the experiment, this study uses attributes that are likely to be present in a real scenario of news navigation. The attributes used are *partisan bias*, *endorser partisanship*, *endorser gender*, and *endorser religiosity*.

Partisan bias of news is determined using the Read Across The Aisle (2022) platform, the use of which is novel in academic research. According to founder, Nick Lum, the platform rates the partisan bias of news using three different sources. These include ratings produced by publications, including the Washington Post, public polling data, including data from Pew Research Center on trust in media outlets by political affiliation, and finally, crowdsourcing (Brightwell, 2017). In the current study partisan bias is measured on a spectrum from 3R to 3D, with 3R representing news which has a very strong Republican bias, N being neutral, and 3D representing news with a very strong Democrat bias. Partisan bias has 7 levels in total.

Endorser partisanship takes one of three values: Democrat, Republican, or Independent. Endorser gender is a binary variable indicating male or female and endorser religiosity is a binary variable to indicate whether the endorser is religious or non-religious. For the purposes of this experiment and the role religiosity plays in attitudes towards abortion, it is deemed unnecessary to state the specific faith of the endorser. The various attributes and levels are shown in *Table 1* below.

Table 1*Attributes and Levels for News Articles in Conjoint Experiment*

<i>Attributes</i>	<i>Values</i>
Political Bias	3R (Very strongly Republican)
	2R (Strongly Republican)
	1R (Somewhat Republican)
	0 Neutral
	1D (Somewhat Democrat)
	2D (Strongly Democrat)
	3D (Very strongly Democrat)
Endorser Partisanship	Republican
	Democrat
	Independent
Endorser Gender	Male
	Female
Endorser Religiosity	Religious
	Not Religious

6.2 Methodology

The methodology follows the statistical approach developed by Hainmueller, Hopkins, & Yamamoto (2014) in estimating the average marginal component effects (AMCE) for the different attributes. The AMCE here represents the average difference in the probability of an article being picked to be read when comparing two different attribute values where the average is taken over all other possible combinations of the other article attributes. The approach to fully randomise the different attribute levels in this study allows for an estimation of the AMCEs using a basic multiple linear regression model. The method involves using a regression of the binary dependent variable on the indicator variables which measure the levels of each attribute.

AMCEs are always interpreted relative to a baseline value of the same attribute. In a linear regression model, the attribute values are essentially treated as categorical variables, with each being dummied out with the baseline set as the omitted category. Here the model can be written as:

$$NS_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PB_i + \beta_2 EP_i + \beta_3 EG_i + \beta_3 ER_i + X_i\gamma + \varepsilon_i$$

Where NS_i is the binary dependent variable indicating news article selection. PB_i is a categorical variable indicating the partisan bias of news, taking on a value as specified above. EP_i is a categorical variable indicating endorser partisanship. EG_i is a binary variable indicating endorser gender. ER_i is a binary variable indicating endorser religiosity. $X_i\gamma$ is a set of socio-demographic control variables, and ε_i is the error term.

Conjoint experiments also allow researchers to calculate conditional AMCEs, which are AMCE's for subgroups on respondents. These subgroups are based on respondent characteristics and in the current study, conditional AMCEs can be calculated based on partisanship. Such insight will answer questions as to whether the determinants of news consumption differ based on an individual's partisanship.

6.2.1 Robustness

The binary dependent variable above is gathered from the forced choice outcome measure in the experiment. Forced choice has been proven an effective tool in conjoint experiments and using a forced choice can encourage participants to think carefully about trade-offs (Bansak, Hainmueller, Hopkins, & Yamamoto, 2019).

Some studies, however, recommend the use of both a forced choice and rating measure concomitantly in order to ensure the robustness of results (Hainmueller & Hopkins, 2015). In these studies, respondents much first choose which option they would rather and then are asked to rate how likely they would be to pick each option, often on a 7-point Likert scale. This variable is then regressed on the attributes to evaluate any differences relative to the forced choice measure.

In the current experiment, a trade-off was faced regarding internal validity. While the inclusion of a rating question as well as forced choice would enable a test of robustness using the rating variable, given the number of choice sets chosen and the length of time this would add to the experiment, it was decided that only a force choice measure would be used. This was done to protect the internal validity of the study against satisficing, which can be a concern in conjoint experiments of too great a length (Bansak, Hainmueller, Hopkins, & Yamamoto, 2021). Thus it was decided that one valid measure is better than two potentially invalid measures.

7. Results

7.1 Respondent Sample

The survey collected a total of 382 responses to be used in the analysis. Our attributes gave us a number of $7 \times 3 \times 2 \times 2 = 84$ possible unique profiles, while our data contains $26 \times 382 = 9,932$ sampled profiles.

The median age of the sample was 36 years and included 186 males and 189 females, with demographic data unavailable for the remaining 7 participants. In terms of partisanship, respondents included 166 Democrats, 68 Republicans, and 132 Independents. 187 participants reported being non-religious while 166 reported being religious.

7.2 Main Analysis

7.2.1 Preferences for Entire Sample

Figure 3 shows the results of the experiment for the total sample. The graph shows the AMCE estimates for each attribute, with one level of each set at the baseline of zero. The line attached to each dot represents a 95% confidence interval and if this line overlaps with zero, the effect is not statistically significant. Dots to the left of the line represent a negative effect of that attribute on the dependent variable, which is the likelihood of an article being chosen to read, relative to the baseline, while dots to the right indicate a positive effect.

Figure 3
Preferences for News Attributes for Entire Sample

Notes: This figure shows estimates of the effects of the randomly assigned article attributes on the probability of being chosen for reading. Estimates are based regression estimators with clustered standard errors. Whiskers attached to each dot represent a 95% confidence interval. The dots without whiskers indicate the attribute value that is the reference category for that attribute.

Table 2 below shows the coefficients for the analysis. As previously mentioned, given full randomisation of attributes, AMCEs can be estimated through a regression of the dependent variable on each attribute variable.

Table 2
Preferences for News Attributes for Entire Sample

	Dependent Variable: 1(article chosen)
N	0.00 (.)
3R	-0.35*** (0.28)
2R	-0.24*** (0.02)
1R	-0.08*** (0.02)
3D	-0.26*** (0.03)
2D	-0.06** (0.02)
1D	-0.18*** (0.02)
Independent	0.00 (.)
Republican	-0.01 (0.01)
Democrat	0.05* (0.02)
Male	0.00 (.)
Female	0.05*** (0.01)
Not Religious	0.00 (.)
Religious	-0.04** (0.01)
Constant	0.68 (0.02)
Observations	382
Adjusted R^2	0.057

Notes: This table reports results for a regression of the dependent variable *chosen_article* on the attribute variables, with the reference category of each attribute included in the table. Standard errors are clustered by respondent. (*: $p < 0.05$, **: $p < 0.01$, ***: $p < 0.001$).

As can be seen from the results, the analysis indicates a general trend away from the most extreme partisan news. Articles with a partisan bias of 3R, that is, very strongly Republican, are 35 percentage points less likely to be chosen for consumption than articles that are N, or, neutral. The effects of articles with 2R and 3D also indicate a trend towards preferring articles that are more moderate.

Regarding endorser characteristics, articles shared by Democrats are favoured over Republicans and Independents, with a bonus of 5 percentage points for Democrats over Independents ($p < 0.05$). Articles shared by females are preferred ($0.05, p < 0.001$) over those shared by males and those endorsed by non-religious individuals are preferred to articles shared by religious individuals, with a penalty of 4 percentage points ($p < 0.01$) for the latter. While these results are insightful, they are likely to mask heterogeneity across different characteristics of the sample. Sample partisanship, religiosity, and gender will now be considered in turn, before reporting the results for Independent respondents only.

7.2.2 Preferences by Respondent Partisanship

Figure 4
Preferences for News Attributes by Partisanship of Respondent

Notes: This figure shows estimates of the effects of the randomly assigned article attributes on the probability of being chosen for reading for Democrats and Republicans. Estimates are based regression estimators with clustered standard errors. Whiskers attached to each dot represent a 95% confidence interval. The dots without whiskers indicate the attribute value that is the reference category for that attribute. See [Appendix D](#) for table with coefficients.

Figure 4 shows the conditional AMCEs for Democrats and Republicans, that is, the AMCEs conditional on respondent partisanship, and it suggests heterogeneity across these categories. Democrats and Republicans respectively show aversion to strongly counter attitudinal partisan news. Democrats show an aversion to all news with a Republican bias, while Republicans avoid news which is very strongly (3D) or strongly (2D) Democrat, but the effect of news that is somewhat Democrat (1D) (-0.05), is not statistically significant from zero. The results indicate that, for Democrats, neutral news and news that is strongly Democrat (2D) is preferred over others, and for Republicans, attitude consistent news is generally preferred over counter attitudinal news, with a lenience for news that is somewhat Democrat.

Regarding endorser partisanship, the results may suggest the presence of in-group bias, with avoidance of out-partisans and seeking of in-partisans observed for both Republicans and Democrats. Interestingly, the avoidance effect seems larger for Republicans than Democrats and the seeking effect larger for Democrats than Republicans. Democrats also show a preference for female endorsers (0.05, $p < 0.01$) and an avoidance of religious endorsers (-0.08, $p < 0.001$), while Republicans prefer articles shared by religious endorsers (0.16, $p < 0.001$).

7.2.3 Preferences by Respondent Religiosity

Figure 5
Preferences for News Attributes by Religiosity of Respondent

Notes: This figure shows estimates of the effects of the randomly assigned article attributes on the probability of being chosen for reading for non-religious and religious respondents. Estimates are based regression estimators with clustered standard errors. Whiskers attached to each dot represent a 95% confidence interval. The dots without whiskers indicate the attribute value that is the reference category for that attribute. See [Appendix E](#) for table with coefficients.

Figure 5 shows the results for non-religious and religious respondents. Non-religious respondents show a preference for neutral articles over all others, while religious respondents show a similar aversion to partisan news with the exception of news that is somewhat Republican, which shows virtually no difference (0.01) with neutral news. When analysing these results, it is helpful to look at the statistics on partisanship and religiosity. Of the 68 Republicans, 55 are religious while 7 are not religious, with the other 6 declining to report their religiosity. 58 Democrats are religious with 100 Democrats non-religious, and 49 and 71 of Independents are religious and non-religious respectively. The non-religious group is therefore mainly comprised of Democrats and Independents, while the religious group contains a fairly even mix of each category.

Non-religious respondents are 9 percentage points more likely to read articles shared by Democrats over those shared by Independents ($p < 0.001$) and 4 percentage points less likely to read those shared by Republicans than Independents ($p < 0.05$). Non-religious participants also prefer news endorsed by females (0.06, $p < 0.001$), while for religious respondents, endorser partisanship and gender effects are not statistically significant. Articles shared by religious individuals carry a penalty of 8 percentage points, significant at the 1% level, relative to articles shared by non-religious endorsers, while the opposite effect is observed for religious respondents (0.07, $p < 0.01$).

7.2.4 Preferences by Respondent Gender

Figure 6
Preferences for News Attributes by Gender of Respondent

Notes: This figure shows estimates of the effects of the randomly assigned article attributes on the probability of being chosen for reading for male and female respondents. Estimates are based regression estimators with clustered standard errors. Whiskers attached to each dot represent a 95% confidence interval. The dots without whiskers indicate the attribute value that is the reference category for that attribute. See [Appendix F](#) for table with coefficients.

Figure 6 shows the analysis for male and female respondents. Broadly, the general trend is observed in both cases, which is expected given the roughly equal number of males and females in the sample. Interestingly, however, is the observation that females are significantly more likely to read news shared by females, with an 11 percentage point increase relative to news shared by males ($p < 0.001$). Another observation is that males avoid news shared by religious endorsers (-0.04 , $p < 0.05$), whereas this does not appear to be the case for female respondents.

7.2.5 Preferences for Independents

Figure 7

Preferences for News Attributes for Independent Respondents

Notes: This figure shows estimates of the effects of the randomly assigned article attributes on the probability of being chosen for reading for Independent respondents. Estimates are based regression estimators with clustered standard errors. Whiskers attached to each dot represent a 95% confidence interval. The dots without whiskers indicate the attribute value that is the reference category for that attribute. See [Appendix G](#) for table with coefficients.

The final analysis in this paper is shown in *Figure 7*, that is, news preferences for Independents. Of the 132 Independents in the study, 60 reported themselves as leaning Democrat, while 27 reported as leaning Republican, with 45 choosing neither. Independent respondents showed a similar trend towards preferring moderate news, with somewhat Republican articles (1R) having an effect (-0.05) that did not statistically significantly differ from zero. This group of respondents did, however, indicate an aversion to Republican endorsers (-0.08, $p < 0.01$), while endorser gender and religiosity did not show significant effects.

8. Discussion

8.1 Implications and Limitations

8.1.1 Seeking and Avoidance

The results give an indication of the role seeking and avoidance plays both in terms of information and endorser characteristics. Regarding information, the general trend was an avoidance of the most extreme partisan news. This is consistent with the relevant statistics on polarisation as, through partisans are becoming more polarised and the ideological overlap is decreasing, in 2014, the overall share of Americans expressing consistently conservative or liberal views was still just over 20%, increasing from 10% in the past two decades (Pew Research Center, 2014). Information avoidance played a larger role in the current study than information seeking, with large effects for the avoidance of counter attitudinal articles, but little statistically significant evidence for preferring attitudinal consistent news. Indeed, effect directions indicate that Republicans preferred Republican-leaning news, but not significantly more than neutral news. Democrats preferred neutral news over every other category, except for news that was strongly Democrat (1D) which did not statistically differ from zero.

Regarding endorser characteristics, the results seemed to overwhelmingly suggest the presence of in-group bias. Democrats and Republicans avoided each other and sought news shared by in-party members, with avoidance and seeking playing a larger role for Republicans and Democrats respectively. Non-religious and religious respondents preferred news shared by those with the same religiosity stance as themselves, and females were more likely to read articles shared by females, though a similar effect was not observed for males. Each of these results would seem to indicate a preference for those perceived as being from the in-group and, in most cases, an avoidance of those perceived as being from the out-group.

8.1.2 Limitations

Though the results presented in the paper are robust, there are several limitations to be discussed. The first is that the dependent variable measuring preferences was measured using self-reported intentions rather than observing actual behaviour. Though conjoint designs have demonstrated to be robust indicators of behaviour (Bansak, Hainmueller, Hopkins & Yamamoto, 2019), the use of self-reporting must be highlighted as a concern. Related to this is the limitation that some attributes are present in a real scenario that weren't included in the experiment. For example, those who share news on social media have a profile and often a picture, and news articles often have a thumbnail image.

Another limitation regarding the dependent variable is the use of a forced choice outcome measure only. As previously mentioned, some studies in this sphere also include a rating outcome measure for each article to enable tests of robustness (Hainmueller & Hopkins, 2015). It was decided, however, that including such a measure in this study could pose threats to internal validity as it could result in satisficing.

Future studies would also benefit from a larger sample size. The current experiment had a respondent sample of 382, of which 68 were Republicans. Though the sample was large enough as recommended by the Sawtooth Guideline (Bock, 2019), the analysis would benefit from a larger number of Republicans which could be achieved by increasing the number of responses collected.

8.1.3 Policy Suggestions

The findings have important implications for policy strategies to encourage more diverse reading behaviour and/or promote depolarisation. *Figure 4* indicates that Republicans may be less concerned with avoiding partisan news than Democrats, with Republicans displaying an openness to reading news that is somewhat Democrat. This could make an intervention like Read Across The Aisle (2022) effective, as Republicans may openly expose themselves to news from the Democrat side of an issue, behaviour which can encourage depolarisation (Levy, 2021; Parsons, 2010). Such an indicator showing the partisan bias of news could be easily implemented on social media platforms.

The results also generally indicate that endorsers of news play a huge role in the decision-making process. The AMCE estimates conditional on group characteristics – partisanship, religiosity, and gender – suggest the presence of in-group bias when browsing news in the form of a tendency to read material shared by individuals of the same group. In terms of the policy interventions discussed above, organisational programs such as The News Literacy Project (2022) could adopt a strategy of encouraging religious leaders or prominent politicians to reach out to their own community to attract people to news literacy education programs.

Regarding the form of must-carry law ruled by the US Supreme Court in the 1970s (Sunstein, 2018), the aversion to news with an out-party partisan bias suggests that news outlets should be encouraged to give both sides of a debate as individuals will be unlikely to encounter such information when sticking to in-party sources. Additionally, those who debate on television or the radio should be encouraged to find some common ground on the issue to set an example to members of their group. In the same vein, politicians could increase the number of bipartisan projects in government to set an example of working together in an effort to reduce intergroup distrust and hostility.

8.2 Suggestions for Further Research

Future studies could address some of the limitations to this experiment. As this study opted for a forced choice dependent variable, another experiment conducted with a rating variable would be a good addition to these findings. Another study could also be undertaken with a larger sample size with the goal of increasing the number of Republican respondents.

Other directions for research involve the use of field experiments. Given the private nature of social media companies, there is a general lack of field experiments by public researchers on the platforms, and private companies like Facebook are often not as forthcoming as would be desirable about their own private research (Wells, Horwitz, & Seetharaman, 2021). That being said, field experiments have been conducted successfully to research echo chambers (Levy, 2021) and misinformation (Pennycook et al., 2021), and a similar approach to investigate news consumption behaviour would be an excellent addition to the literature in this space.

9. Conclusion

The aim of this study was to shed light on people's preferences for news attributes surrounding abortion-related news in the aftermath of the recent US Supreme Court overruling of *Roe v. Wade*. This was achieved through the use of a conjoint experiment testing the effect of various attributes that are present when individuals consume news on social media. Many of the findings provide a valuable contribution to the theories of information seeking and avoidance, and in-group bias, with news preferences largely depicting a story of avoiding the out-group while seeking the in-group.

The study contributes to the behavioural science literature surrounding political polarisation and news consumption by revealing those attributes that are most influential in guiding people's behaviour, and illuminating those policies that are most effective in encouraging more diverse reading. The study also employed a partisan bias measure, the use of which is novel in academic research, paving the way for further studies investigating the partisan bias of news. Conjoint experiments are a relatively recent and innovative tool in the political science literature, and the use of the partisan bias measure in this experiment continues that philosophy of innovation to keep academic research at the forefront of knowledge creation.

The topic of abortion was a suitable one for this study, as opinions are highly variable yet consistent across group lines. It is also one of the most hotly debated ethical issues of our time, and this study provides insights which could illuminate a pathway to a more measured, considered discourse that is so needed, yet often missing, in public life.

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Appendix

Appendix A

Items in the 10-item scale of political values

Question #	Conservative position	[OR]	Liberal position
Q25a	Government is almost always wasteful and inefficient		Government often does a better job than people give it credit for
Q25b	Government regulation of business usually does more harm than good		Government regulation of business is necessary to protect the public interest
Q25c	Poor people today have it easy because they can get government benefits without doing anything in return		Poor people have hard lives because government benefits don't go far enough to help them live decently
Q25d	The government today can't afford to do much more to help the needy		The government should do more to help needy Americans, even if it means going deeper into debt
Q25f	Blacks who can't get ahead in this country are mostly responsible for their own condition		Racial discrimination is the main reason why many black people can't get ahead these days
Q25g	Immigrants today are a burden on our country because they take our jobs, housing and health care		Immigrants today strengthen our country because of their hard work and talents
Q25i	The best way to ensure peace is through military strength		Good diplomacy is the best way to ensure peace
Q25n	Most corporations make a fair and reasonable amount of profit		Business corporations make too much profit
Q50r	Stricter environmental laws and regulations cost too many jobs and hurt the economy		Stricter environmental laws and regulations are worth the cost
Q50u	Homosexuality should be discouraged by society		Homosexuality should be accepted by society

Source: Pew Research Center (2017)

Appendix B

Classification of 124 Published Articles Using Conjoint Designs in Political Science

Topic	Percentage
Voting	27%
Public Opinion	19%
Public Policy	6%
Immigration	6%
Government	6%
Climate Change	6%
Representation	5%
International Relations	5%
Partisanship	4%
Other	17%

Source: Bansak, Hainmueller, Hopkins, & Yamamoto (2019)

Appendix C

Full Experimental Materials – Informed Consent

In this study, you are asked to choose which news articles you would rather read if you were browsing social media.

The study should take around 10 minutes to complete. Participation is voluntary and you can withdraw from the study at any stage.

Feel free to contact Thomas Walsh at t.walsh1@lse.ac.uk should you have any questions.

By choosing to participate, you acknowledge that your participation is voluntary, you are at least 18 years of age, speak English fluently, and you are aware you can withdraw at any time.

- No, I do not want to participate
- Yes, I want to participate

Appendix C

Full Experimental Materials (continued) – Demographic Questions

Prolific ID Enter your unique Prolific ID

What is the highest level of education you have completed?

- No formal education
- High school or equivalent
- Undergraduate degree (BA/BSc/Other)
- Graduate degree (MA/MSc/PhD/Other)
- Professional degree (JD/MD/Other)

What is your religion?

- Catholic
- Protestant
- Christian other
- Buddhist
- Jewish
- Hindu
- No religion
- Other
- Prefer not to say

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Appendix C

Full Experimental Materials (continued) – Partisanship Questions

Generally speaking, what do you think of yourself as?

- Democrat
- Republican
- Independent
- Other

Display This Question:

If Generally speaking, what do you think of yourself as? = Independent

Or Generally speaking, what do you think of yourself as? = Other

If you had to choose, do you think of yourself as closer to the Democrat or Republican Party?

- Democrat
- Republican
- Neither

Display This Question:

If Generally speaking, what do you think of yourself as? = Democrat

Would you call yourself a strong Democrat or a not very strong Democrat?

- Strong
- Not very strong

Appendix C

Full Experimental Materials (continued) – Partisanship Questions (continued)

Display This Question:

If Generally speaking, what do you think of yourself as? = Republican

Would you call yourself a strong Republican or a not very strong Republican?

- Strong
- Not very strong

demlike On a scale of 1 to 100, how much do you like Democrats?

0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100

0 (Not at all) to 100 (Very much so) ()

replike On a scale of 1 to 100, how much do you like Republicans?

0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100

0 (Not at all) to 100 (Very much so) ()

Appendix C

Full Experimental Materials (continued) – Conjoint Task

In the following tasks, you will be presented with pairs of news articles that differ in a number of characteristics.

You are asked to act if you were browsing social media, and to pick which article you would be more likely to read.

The study consists of 13 pairs.

Article A	Source and Headline	Article B
<i>The Economist</i>		<i>Fox News</i>
'The fallout from overturning Roe'		'The abortion industry preys on Black women'
Independent	Endorser Partisanship	Republican
Male	Endorser Gender	Female
Not Religious	Endorser Religiosity	Religious

Which article would you be more likely to read when browsing social media?

A

B

Article A	Source and Headline	Article B
<i>The New York Times</i>		<i>Fox News</i>
'Biden's health secretary calls abortion ruling despicable'		'Courageous Supreme Court's abortion ruling makes history'
Independent	Endorser Partisanship	Republican
Female	Endorser Gender	Male
Religious	Endorser Religiosity	Not Religious

Which article would you be more likely to read when browsing social media?

A

B

Appendix C

Full Experimental Materials (continued) – Conjoint Task (continued)

Article A	Source and Headline	Article B
<i>The Economist</i>		<i>Huffington Post</i>
'America's abortion providers face a fight for survival'		'Biden supports exception to filibuster to codify Roe v. Wade'
Republican	Endorser Partisanship	Democrat
Female	Endorser Gender	Male
Not Religious	Endorser Religiosity	Religious

Which article would you be more likely to read when browsing social media?

A

B

Article A	Source and Headline	Article B
<i>Fox News</i>		<i>The National Review</i>
'The abortion industry doesn't want you to hear these facts'		'Abortion and the restoration of democracy'
Independent	Endorser Partisanship	Democrat
Male	Endorser Gender	Female
Religious	Endorser Religiosity	Not Religious

Which article would you be more likely to read when browsing social media?

A

B

Appendix C

Full Experimental Materials (continued) – Conjoint Task (continued)

Article A	Source and Headline	Article B
<i>Fox News</i>		<i>Reuters</i>
'Pro-abortion groups target churches for Mother's Day protests'		'Abortion bans force U.S. students to rethink college plans'
Independent	Endorser Partisanship	Republican
Female	Endorser Gender	Male
Not Religious	Endorser Religiosity	Religious

Which article would you be more likely to read when browsing social media?

- A
- B

Article A	Source and Headline	Article B
<i>The New York Times</i>		<i>Huffington Post</i>
'If Roe falls, Is same-sex marriage next?'		'Biden slams decision overturning Roe v. Wade'
Republican	Endorser Partisanship	Democrat
Male	Endorser Gender	Female
Religious	Endorser Religiosity	Not Religious

Which article would you be more likely to read when browsing social media?

- A
- B

Appendix C

Full Experimental Materials (continued) – Conjoint Task (continued)

Article A	Source and Headline	Article B
<i>The Washington Post</i> 'Democrats cannot afford to lose focus on abortion'		<i>The National Review</i> 'Abortion supporters, end the violence'
Democrat	Endorser Partisanship	Republican
Male	Endorser Gender	Female
Not Religious	Endorser Religiosity	Religious

Which article would you be more likely to read when browsing social media?

A

B

Article A	Source and Headline	Article B
<i>The New York Times</i> 'The long path to reclaim abortion rights'		<i>The Washington Post</i> 'Why we're still arguing about abortion and regret'
Democrat	Endorser Partisanship	Independent
Female	Endorser Gender	Male
Not Religious	Endorser Religiosity	Religious

Which article would you be more likely to read when browsing social media?

A

B

Appendix C

Full Experimental Materials (continued) – Conjoint Task (continued)

Article A	Source and Headline	Article B
<i>The New York Times</i>	<i>The National Review</i>	
'Inside the extreme effort to punish women for abortion'	'Don't listen to Europe on abortion'	
Democrat	Endorser Partisanship	Independent
Female	Endorser Gender	Male
Religious	Endorser Religiosity	Not Religious

Which article would you be more likely to read when browsing social media?

A

B

Article A	Source and Headline	Article B
<i>The Washington Post</i>	<i>The Economist</i>	
'Explainer: What's next for abortion pills after the fall of Roe'	'Most Americans disagree with the Supreme Court on abortion'	
Independent	Endorser Partisanship	Democrat
Female	Endorser Gender	Male
Religious	Endorser Religiosity	Not Religious

Which article would you be more likely to read when browsing social media?

A

B

Article A	Source and Headline	Article B
<i>The Economist</i>	<i>The New York Times</i>	
'Around the world, bans do not make abortion much rarer'	'Athletes, players unions and leagues criticize abortion ruling'	
Republican	Endorser Partisanship	Independent
Female	Endorser Gender	Male
Religious	Endorser Religiosity	Not Religious

Which article would you be more likely to read when browsing social media?

A

B

Appendix C

Full Experimental Materials (continued) – Conjoint Task (continued)

Article A	Source and Headline	Article B
<i>The Washington Post</i>		<i>Reuters</i>
'Mississippi's last abortion clinic will shutter as trigger ban begins'		'U.S. House panel to investigate companies sharing reproductive data'
Democrat	Endorser Partisanship	Independent
Male	Endorser Gender	Female
Religious	Endorser Religiosity	Not Religious

Which article would you be more likely to read when browsing social media?

A

B

Article A	Source and Headline.	Article B
<i>The Washington Post</i>		<i>Fox News</i>
'Christian activists push for total abortion ban in South Carolina'		'Abortion ruling a reminder that civil rights begin in the womb'
Republican	Endorser Partisanship	Independent
Female	Endorser Gender	Male
Not Religious	Endorser Religiosity	Religious

Which article would you be more likely to read when browsing social media?

A

B

Appendix D

Preferences for News Attributes by Partisanship of Respondent

Dependent Variable: 1(article chosen)		
	Democrats	Republicans
N	0.00 (.)	0.00 (.)
3R	-0.53*** (0.04)	-0.00 (0.06)
2R	-0.44*** (0.03)	-0.01 (0.05)
1R	-0.19*** (0.03)	0.02 (0.04)
3D	-0.43*** (0.03)	-0.12* (0.06)
2D	-0.05 (0.03)	-0.17*** (0.03)
1D	-0.27*** (0.03)	-0.05 (0.05)
Independent	0.00 (.)	0.00 (.)
Republican	-0.04* (0.02)	0.08* (0.04)
Democrat	0.19*** (0.02)	-0.22*** (0.04)
Male	0.00 (.)	0.00 (.)
Female	0.05** (0.02)	0.04 (0.03)
Not Religious	0.00 (.)	0.00 (.)
Religious	-0.08*** (0.02)	0.16*** (0.03)
Constant	0.75 (0.03)	0.49 (0.04)
Observations	166	68
Adjusted R^2	0.195	0.130

Notes: This table reports results for a regression of the dependent variable *chosen_article* on the attribute variables by partisanship of respondent, with the reference category of each attribute included in the table. Standard errors are clustered by respondent. (*: $p < 0.05$, **: $p < 0.01$, ***: $p < 0.001$).

Appendix E

Preferences for News Attributes by Religiosity of Respondent

	Dependent Variable: 1(article chosen)	
	Not Religious	Religious
N	0.00 (.)	0.00 (.)
3R	-0.53*** (0.03)	-0.16*** (0.04)
2R	-0.40*** (0.03)	-0.14*** (0.04)
1R	-0.19*** (0.03)	0.01 (0.03)
3D	-0.41*** (0.03)	-0.20*** (0.04)
2D	-0.10*** (0.02)	-0.06* (0.03)
1D	-0.28*** (0.03)	-0.12*** (0.03)
Independent	0.00 (.)	0.00 (.)
Republican	-0.04* (0.02)	-0.03 (0.02)
Democrat	0.09*** (0.02)	-0.01 (0.03)
Male	0.00 (.)	0.00 (.)
Female	0.06*** (0.02)	0.02 (0.02)
Not Religious	0.00 (.)	0.00 (.)
Religious	-0.08*** (0.02)	0.07** (0.02)
Constant	0.78 (0.03)	0.57 (0.03)
Observations	187	166
Adjusted R^2	0.143	0.018

Notes: This table reports results for a regression of the dependent variable *chosen article* on the attribute variables by religiosity of respondent, with the reference category of each attribute included in the table. Standard errors are clustered by respondent. (*: $p < 0.05$, **: $p < 0.01$, ***: $p < 0.001$).

Appendix F

Preferences for News Attributes by Gender of Respondent

Dependent Variable: 1(article chosen)		
	Male	Female
N	0.00 (.)	0.00 (.)
3R	-0.33*** (0.04)	-0.36*** (0.04)
2R	-0.23*** (0.03)	-0.31*** (0.03)
1R	-0.09*** (0.03)	-0.10** (0.03)
3D	-0.27*** (0.04)	-0.34*** (0.03)
2D	-0.06* (0.02)	-0.10*** (0.03)
1D	-0.17*** (0.03)	-0.22*** (0.03)
Independent	0.00 (.)	0.00 (.)
Republican	-0.04 (0.02)	-0.03 (0.02)
Democrat	0.00 (0.03)	0.06* (0.03)
Male	0.00 (.)	0.00 (.)
Female	-0.02 (0.02)	0.11*** (0.02)
Not Religious	0.00 (.)	0.00 (.)
Religious	-0.04* (0.02)	0.00 (0.02)
Constant	0.71 (0.03)	0.64 (0.03)
Observations	187	189
Adjusted R^2	0.049	0.074

Notes: This table reports results for a regression of the dependent variable *chosen article* on the attribute variables by gender of respondent, with the reference category of each attribute included in the table. Standard errors are clustered by respondent. (*: $p < 0.05$, **: $p < 0.01$, ***: $p < 0.001$).

Appendix G

Preferences for News Attributes for Independents

	Dependent Variable: 1(article chosen)
N	0.00 (.)
3R	-0.31*** (0.04)
2R	-0.21*** (0.04)
1R	-0.05 (0.03)
3D	-0.25*** (0.04)
2D	-0.08** (0.03)
1D	-0.19*** (0.03)
Independent	0.00 (.)
Republican	-0.08** (0.02)
Democrat	-0.02 (0.03)
Male	0.00 (.)
Female	0.02 (0.02)
Not Religious	0.00 (.)
Religious	-0.03 (0.02)
Constant	0.70 (0.03)
Observations	132
Adjusted R^2	0.046

Notes: This table reports results for a regression of the dependent variable *chosen_article* on the attribute variables for Independent respondents, with the reference category of each attribute included in the table. Standard errors are clustered by respondent. (*: $p < 0.05$, **: $p < 0.01$, ***: $p < 0.001$).